

TEACHING ENGLISH AS A PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION IN THE LANGUAGE OF TECHNICAL-MECHANIC EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the essence and important aspects of the combined model of traditional and non-traditional educational technologies, as well as the innovative methodology of joint calculation of sturgeons for consistency and uniformity using the method of initial parameters. Also, it is proven that the use of the indicated tablet program is highly effective in education.

Every country that is on the path of development and progress emphasizes, first of all, on raising the young generation to become perfect and mature people in all respects. It is appropriate to emphasize that the educational system has a special role in achieving this goal.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, suggested that learning foreign languages should be made a priority. "For this purpose, in the coming year, systematic work will be carried out, such as radically improving the quality of teaching these subjects, opening specialized schools, and attracting qualified pedagogues" [1].

In fact, raising the quality of education in teaching the young generation, using new modern methods in foreign language classes, increasing students' motivation and becoming a competitive staff in the future are the main tasks for every teacher. The activation of the competence approach to education in world pedagogy has become one of the urgent tasks of developing communicative competences in the formation of professional competence of future specialists in higher education, and in the process of preparing students for professional activities, developing their professional speech. It is important for today's specialist to be able to communicate effectively in his future activities, to be competent and competitive according to international standards.

During the consistent reforms carried out in the years of independence, special attention has been paid to inculcating patriotic ideas in the youth of our country, directing them to the profession and developing their culture. However, we are witnessing that the teaching of professional sectoral culture is somewhat left aside. It is no secret that the culture of

professional communication in a foreign language is not sufficient for the employees working in the field of technology and business, as well as representatives of production, economy, tourism, banking, education and other fields. In particular, it is one of the urgent problems that the future personnel directly conduct verbal, written and official documents with qualified foreign specialists. From this point of view, organization of language education of technical-mechanics students in a career-oriented way, development of professional speech communication competences of future specialists acquires important scientific and practical importance.

We will briefly touch on the following didactic requirements for training. First, educational goals should be defined clearly, clearly, consistently and fluently. In turn, it is necessary to determine the content of education, to adapt it to the standards of the science program, DTS requirements, to form skills and competences and competences of students while acquiring knowledge, to choose the appropriate methods, methods and methods and educational tools based on the content of education, and to successfully achieve results. Creating an environment is very important. Successful implementation of these didactic requirements requires didactic skills from the teacher.

It is self-evident that among all subjects, creating new generation textbooks for students of technical higher and secondary special, vocational education institutions, including general subjects, developing didactic requirements for their testing and putting them into practice is one of the urgent problems that cannot be delayed. In addition, the theory of creating a textbook is also a theory of education at a certain level. Here, in the theory of education, it is important that the modern textbook is considered a set of information model and incorporates the four important components of the pedagogical system consisting of the pedagogue - textbook - educational process - pupil-student.

The principle of teaching to acquire knowledge, skills and competences in a conscious manner is the realization by learners of how important knowledge, skills and competences are in society and in human life, not mechanically memorizing, but actively thinking and mastering the content of educational materials. listening and putting them into practice in their place.

This is explained as follows: when creating a textbook based on this principle, first of all, special attention should be paid to enriching learners with materials that activate them during lessons or independent learning processes. Also, in order to strengthen the knowledge gained in the course of teaching in the textbook, and in the end, to put it into practice, materials that encourage students to acquire knowledge: exercises in English aimed at active thinking, not mechanical memorization, and listening to the essence of the studied materials, as well as knowledge control it is appropriate to provide samples of questions and tasks designed to ensure an objective, fair, fast and competent assessment. As a result, it is possible to ensure that students understand the importance of acquiring the knowledge, skills and competences intended to be mastered, understand their practical importance and, most importantly, apply them in practice.

In the Concept "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019, UP-5847, it is noted "... the

introduction of advanced standards of higher education, in particular a phased transition from education, which are aimed at obtaining theoretical knowledge, to the education system, aimed at the formation of practical skills, based on international experience. " This confirms the relevance of considering, firstly, that the training of qualified, competitive personnel for real sectors of the economy has become one of the priorities of state policy, and secondly, the unity of modern teaching and learning processes as a strict technological process from a pedagogical point of view, along with the elimination of the pandemic coronavirus that entered our country from abroad.

The essence of this model, first of all, shows that traditional and non-traditional educational technologies have common features, such as didactics, content and form of education, quality and efficiency, in providing a holistic educational trinity in the form of "Purpose - process (tool) - result"

The didactic process determines the basis of pedagogical technology, that is, its content is a mechanism for transferring the content of teaching to the learner over a certain period of time. Naturally, the construction of a didactic process requires, first of all, special pedagogical skills and potential, attention from the teacher, as well as didactic abilities for the full fulfillment of didactic requirements.

The peculiarity of the didactic process is that this process begins as soon as the active phase of activity appears - motivation, which can attract the attention of students as soon as the lesson begins, regardless of whether the forms of education are traditional or non-traditional or an individual. This stage of motivation should be considered as the key to educational and cognitive activities.

The results of pedagogical and psychological research and observations confirm that the didactic process consists of the following three interrelated components: motivation, student learning and teacher management (often typical of the traditional learning model), coordination, support and counseling. The teacher needs to know exactly what level of motivation corresponds to the purpose and content of each lesson. There are actually many different ways to increase your motivation. For example, communicating problem situations to students at the beginning of the lesson is the simplest approach.

Secondly, ensuring the continuity of the continuity of education in a combination of theory and practice within the framework of the requirements of educational standards confirms that this depends on such factors as the activities of a modern teacher, material and technical conditions, and teaching methods.

The importance of the model lies, firstly, the separate application in practice of authoritarian and student-centered learning technologies used in the system of lifelong education, secondly, to modernize it, while maintaining the traditional learning model, and to increase the efficiency of its use, thirdly, if necessary, the implementation of educational processes according to the principle of harmonization of both teaching methods.

When the traditional teaching model is used, the purpose of the lesson becomes clear, the tasks or set of tasks are prepared mainly in the form of a sample, the algorithm of which is transmitted to students in a predetermined order. The educational activity of students is under pedagogical influence, and teaching is "supposedly" obligatory. In other words, the transmission of information is passive, that their ability to think critically and logically, creatively is limited in the context of independent learning.

It is extremely important to achieve the correct use of field terms in speech when teaching the culture of professional communication in the language of technical-mechanic education. Based on this, we have developed a three-stage system of developing the skills of using industry terms. This system is aimed at introducing the terms from the inactive lexicon to the active lexicon of the students step by step, and at the first stage, the student will master the terms with the help of the teacher, at the second stage, he will start using them independently in the speech, and at the third stage, he will have the skills to use them freely in the speech process.

If the following methods and rules are followed, the first exercises, and thus professional skills, are effectively formed:

- assignment - those performing the actions mentally "speak to themselves verbally" while concentrating their memory;
- guidance (instructions) or road maps - strictly follow the instructions of the educator or teacher while performing the actions, even if it is difficult to do, to realize by heart the importance of the actions and not to make mistakes in this regard later;
- oral analysis of errors and defects, their causes and methods of elimination;

- verbal or written justification of the chosen method (method) of performing actions, etc.

Conclusion. Knowledge created on the basis of the requirements of the State Education Standard and the Network Education Standard, covering the basic educational materials specified in the relevant science program, inculcating the idea of national independence, relying on didactic principles, having a specific research topic and research methods (methods, methods) and becoming a belief, Pedagogical-psychological and information technologies aimed at forming competence, which is considered as the base set of skills, quality, independent search for the necessary learning materials aimed at independent mastering by learners, development of creative abilities while teaching their application in practical activities, and formation of certain human qualities of learners It is a source of knowledge that can be created on the basis of, and in necessary cases can show the characteristics of flexibility and variability in harmony with modern innovative production, and finally, most importantly, it will bring the individual to guaranteed results.

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